

**EFFICIENT 3-D FINITE ELEMENT FAILURE ANALYSIS OF
COMPRESSION LOADED ANGLE-PLY PLATES WITH HOLES**

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ABSTRACT

Finite element stress analysis and the tensor polynomial failure criterion predict that failure always initiates at the interface between layers on the hole edge for notched angle-ply laminates loaded in compression. The angular location of initial failure is a function of the fiber orientation in the laminate. The dominate stress components initiating failure are shear. It is shown that approximate symmetry can be used to reduce the computer resources required for the case of uniaxial loading.

INTRODUCTION

The class of composite laminates known as angle-ply laminates illustrates a basic advantage of composite materials, the ability to tailor laminate stiffness and strength by varying the orientation of the fibers in the individual layers. Use of this property in design of notched laminates requires a thorough knowledge and understanding of the strength properties as a function of fiber orientation, stacking sequence, notch geometry, and loading configuration.

Failure of notched laminates has been considered previously by a number of investigators. The previous works have included micromechanics, plane stress of homogeneous anisotropic plates, and 3-D stress analysis including interlaminar stresses. Various failure theories have been proposed also. A review of the pertinent literature can be found in reference [1]. Previous works on compression loaded plates includes those by Rhodes et al [2] and Shuart and Williams [3]. To the authors' knowledge there has been no previous systematic study on notched, angle-ply laminates as a family.

In the present study, we consider the case of far-field compression

loading of $[\pm \phi]_S$ laminates with a circular hole (Fig. 1). Compression loading was chosen because it is, so often, the controlling factor in the design of aerospace structures which experience both tension and compression. Compression is usually the controlling design consideration because composites generally exhibit significantly lower strength in compression than in tension. Angle-ply laminates were chosen to isolate the influence of fiber orientation. The stacking sequence was held constant throughout the study.

This paper presents the results of a finite element investigation of the full three-dimensional stress distribution with emphasis on the interlaminar stresses around the hole boundary. Four laminates are considered: $[\pm 10]_S$, $[\pm 20]_S$, $[\pm 30]_S$, and $[\pm 45]_S$. The main objective of the study was to determine the states of stress and to relate the stress states to failure of the laminates. The discussion of the stress states given here focuses on the stresses around the hole edge because it is known that failure initiates on the hole boundary [1].

Because of limitations of the idealized analysis used, the study of failure emphasizes the prediction of the location and mode of failure as opposed to the critical load. Results concerning the use of approximate symmetry conditions show how the analysis can be made more efficient while not losing the character of the failure analysis.

FIG 1 Notched Plate Under Compression

FIG 2 Quarter Symmetric Finite Element Mesh

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The axes of orthotropy of the laminae are not aligned with the global

X or Y axes (Fig. 1). Hence, the laminates studied here do not exhibit reflection symmetry about either of these global axes. Therefore, an exact model of the problem would require a finite element mesh comprising the entire half of the laminate above (or below) the midplane. Such a mesh could not be used because of the large computer storage and long running times required for such a model. Instead, the Y axis was taken to be an axis of approximate reflection symmetry. The rationale for this approximation will be discussed.

The finite element model is based on the assumptions of linear elastic material behavior and linear strain-displacement relationships. The model assumes a distinct interface between plies. Each ply was divided into three layers of 16 node elements (Fig. 2). Stresses were output at the center of each layer of elements, giving six locations through the thickness of the laminate at which stresses could be obtained. Stresses and strains were calculated at the element Gauss points and at points on the element boundaries, making it possible to obtain the distribution of stress directly on the hole boundary.

The material properties used in the analysis (Table 1) are typical of AS4/3502 graphite-epoxy.

TABLE 1 - Properties of AS4/3502 Graphite-Epoxy

Elastic Properties

$E_1 = 19.85$ msi	$E_2 = E_3 = 1.53$ msi	$G_{12} = G_{13} = 0.85$ msi
$G_{23} = 0.60$ msi	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.32$	$\nu_{23} = 0.40$

Strength Properties

$X_c = -122.4$ ksi	$Y_c = Z_c = -34.6$ ksi	$S_{12} = S_{13} = 9.4$ ksi
	$S_{23} = 8.0$ ksi	

SYMMETRY CONSIDERATIONS

The use of 1/4 and 1/8 symmetry models was studied in an effort to reduce the computer resources required while still obtaining satisfactory results. Figures 3 and 4 show the distribution of $\tau_{\theta z}$ and σ_{θ} at $z = 5H/12$ around the edge of a hole in a $[\pm 30]_s$ laminate for both symmetry assumptions. It is obvious from the figures that the assumption of 1/8 symmetry artificially imposes a severe restriction on both stress components near $\theta = 0$. The artificial constraint causes very large gradients and a sign change for both stresses. These gradients were deemed unacceptable both because of their magnitude and their location, which is near the experimentally observed failure location [1].

In contrast to the large gradients at $\theta = 0$ in the 1/8 symmetry model, relatively small gradients are present at $\theta = \pm 90^\circ$ in the 1/4 symmetry model. It was also verified that the adverse effects of the symmetry approximation were limited to the elements adjacent to the line of assumed symmetry. Since $\theta = \pm 90^\circ$ is far from the failure point in all laminates, the 1/4 symmetry model was judged to be satisfactory for the purpose of this study. The use of the 1/4 symmetry model resulted in significant efficiencies of computer resources.

FIG 3 $\tau_{\theta z}$ vs θ at $z = 5H/12$
for $[\pm 30]_S$ Laminate

FIG 4 σ_z vs θ at $z = 5H/12$
for $[\pm 30]_S$ Laminate

STRESS ANALYSIS

The primary goal of this study was the prediction of failure, hence, stress are presented primarily in the material (1-2-3) coordinate system. This facilitates the evaluation of different failure criteria more directly. Also, since failure initiates on the hole boundary, stresses are presented as distributions around the hole edge at a particular through-the-thickness location.

In the following discussion, the distributions of the inplane stress components, σ_1 , σ_2 , and τ_{12} , are presented at the center of a layer. The interlaminar shear stresses τ_{13} and τ_{23} are presented for z locations near the $\pm \varphi$ interface. Results for the interlaminar normal stress σ_3 (also σ_{z2}) are presented near the laminate midplane ($z=0$). All of the above locations were chosen because they correspond to the largest magnitudes of the stresses. The only difference between inplane stresses in a $+\varphi$ and those in a $-\varphi$ layer is a reflection about $\theta = 0$. Interlaminar stresses are, of course, continuous across the interface. All stresses have been determined for an applied axial strain $\epsilon_x = -0.1\%$. Stress concentrations are normalized with respect to the far-field applied stress $\bar{\sigma}_y$.

Axial Stresses σ_1

The distributions of σ_1 , on the hole edge in the center of the $-\phi$ plies, are shown in Fig. 5. From the figure it can be seen that both the magnitudes and the locations of the maximum values are functions of fiber orientation. The maximum magnitude occurs for the $[\pm 10]_s$ laminate at an angle $\theta = \pm 10^\circ$ where there is a strong local maximum. The locations of the maximum values for different fiber orientations range from 10° for the $[\pm 10]_s$ laminate to 37.5° for the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate. The range of stress concentration factors ($\sigma_1/\bar{\sigma}_y$) ranges from 6.22 for the $[\pm 10]_s$ laminate to 5.06 for the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate. The maximum σ_1 stress in the $[\pm 10]_s$ laminate is an order of magnitude higher than that in the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate. All maximum stresses are compressive.

Transverse Stress σ_2

The distributions of σ_2 in the center of the $-\phi$ plies of the four laminates are shown in Fig. 6. The maximum σ_2 stress is an order of magnitude lower than the maximum σ_1 . This is due to the low transverse modulus. Also, the σ_2 gradients are much less severe than those for σ_1 . The transverse stress can be positive or negative depending upon the θ value. In general, σ_2 is compressive for low to medium values of θ and tensile for higher θ values. The maximum tensile values are at $\theta = \pm 90^\circ$ where the artificial symmetry constraint was imposed. The maximum stress concentration $\sigma_2/\bar{\sigma}_y$ is -0.37 for the $[\pm 30]_s$ laminate. Recall that the maximum $\sigma_1/\bar{\sigma}_y$ was 6.22 for the $[\pm 10]_s$ laminate.

FIG 5 σ_1 vs θ , at $r=a$, $z=H/4$

FIG 6 σ_2 vs θ , at $r=a$, $z=H/4$

Inplane Shear Stress τ_{12}

The circumferential distributions of τ_{12} on the hole edge are shown in Fig. 7. The stresses in the - and + ϕ layers (not shown) are reflections about the lines $\theta = 0$ and $\tau_{12} = 0$. The stresses are low in comparison to σ_1 values. The magnitude and location of the maximum values are functions of fiber orientation. The stress concentration $\tau_{12}/\bar{\sigma}_y$ varies from a maximum of 1.0 for the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate to a minimum of 0.6 for the $[\pm 10]_s$ laminate. The absolute maximum shear stress τ_{12} occurs in the $[\pm 10]_s$ laminate at $\theta = 0$.

Interlaminar Shear Stresses τ_{13} and τ_{23}

The distributions of the interlaminar shear stresses are shown in Fig. 8 and 9. These stresses are plotted for $z = 5H/12$, which is the location of the Gauss point nearest the $\pm \phi$ interface, and in the - ϕ layer. These interlaminar shear stresses are of the same order of magnitude as the transverse stresses. The distribution of τ_{13} is approximately symmetric about the line $\theta = 0$ where there is a relatively strong peak. The maximum stress concentration $\tau_{13}/\bar{\sigma}_y$ varies over a small range from 0.85 for the $[\pm 20]_s$ laminate to 0.6 for the $[\pm 10]_s$ laminate. The distribution of τ_{23} does not exhibit the same approximate symmetry, although there is an approximately symmetric peak about $\theta = 0$. The range of stress concentrations $\tau_{23}/\bar{\sigma}_y$ is from 0.70 for the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate to 0.11 for the $[\pm 10]_s$ laminate. The absolute maximums for both τ_{13} and τ_{23} occur in the $[\pm 20]_s$ laminate at $\pm 2.5^\circ$ and $\pm 5^\circ$, respectively.

FIG 7 τ_{12} vs θ , at $r=a$, $z=H/4$

FIG 8 τ_{13} vs θ , at $r=a$, $z=5H/12$

Interlaminar Normal Stress σ_3

The distributions of σ_3 (Fig. 10) are given at $z = H/12$ which corresponds to the Gauss point nearest the laminate midplane. These stresses are very small in magnitude. The large gradient in σ_3 at $\theta = \pm 90$ are due to the artificially imposed symmetry condition and can be ignored. Because of the extremely low magnitude of these stresses, they will not be discussed further.

FAILURE PREDICTIONS

Failure was predicted on the bases of the tensor polynomial failure criterion [4]. A load factor R was defined to be the positive root of the quadratic equation describing the failure criterion:

$$F_i \sigma_i R + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j R^2 = 1$$

FIG 9 τ_{23} vs θ , at $r=a$, $z=5H/12$

FIG 10 σ_3 vs θ , at $r=a$, $z=H/12$

Every point in the finite element model has a load factor associated with failure at that point. The point with the minimum load factor (R^{\min}) is the point at which failure is first predicted to occur. The minimum load factor, R^{\min} , when multiplied by the far-field strain used in the finite element analysis, (-0.1%), gives the predicted far-field first failure strain. The stresses used in the failure analysis were corrected to provide better satisfaction of the stress-free boundary conditions on the hole edge. The rationale for the corrections is fully discussed and justified in reference [1].

A thorough investigation of the thru-the-thickness variations indicated that failure was always predicted to initiate at the Gauss points closest to the interface. Figures 11 and 12 show the variation in the

normalized load factor, above and below the interfaces, as a function of location about the hole edge for all four angle-ply laminates. Also presented in each figure are the far-field strains corresponding to first failure of each laminate. Table 2 presents numerical values for the θ location of the initial failure, the corresponding far-field strain, and each term in the tensor polynomial.

The results show that there is excellent correlation between the far-field failure initiation strain as predicted above and below the interface. This is particularly significant because, as indicated in the figures and the table, the location relative to the horizontal axis ($\theta=0$) is a function of both the fiber orientation and which side of the interface is considered. For the 10° laminate failure is predicted at $\theta=0$ on both sides of the interface; however, as the fiber angle is increased, the location of initial failure moves away from the horizontal axis, being generally symmetric about the axis in the + and - ϕ layers. These predicted failure locations are in good agreement with experimental observations [1].

FIG 11 R^{\min}/R vs θ , at $r=a$, $z=5H/12$

FIG 12 R^{\min}/R vs θ , at $r=a$, $z=7H/12$

Close examination of the individual terms of the tensor polynomial in Table 2 indicates that the τ_{12} term is the largest contributor to the polynomial in all laminates. For the ± 45 laminate, this term is essentially equal to or greater than 1.0 on both sides of the interface. For all other laminates, failure is predicted to be, primarily, a combination of both τ_{12} and τ_{13} . For the $[\pm 10]_s$ laminate, the σ_1 term is also significant indicating the possibility of fiber compressive failure. Thus, failure in notched angle-ply laminates is predicted to be primarily a shear dominated event with one inplane shear component and one interlaminar shear component playing an important role.

TABLE 2 - Terms in Corrected-Stress
Tensor Polynomial at Failure
in Notched Angle-Ply Laminates
($r = a$)

Laminate	$[\pm 10]_s$	$[\pm 20]_s$	$[\pm 30]_s$	$[\pm 45]_s$
Z	5H/12 7H/12	5H/12 7H/12	5H/12 7H/12	5H/12 7H/12
θ_c	0.0 0.0	2.5 -5.0	7.5 -10.0	22.5 -22.5
$\epsilon^u(\%)$	-0.0475 -0.0475	-0.0559 -0.0549	-0.0942 -0.0922	-0.2330 -0.2364
$F_1\sigma_1$	0.1315 0.1313	0.0707 0.0805	0.0603 0.0622	0.0718 0.0214
$F_{11}\sigma_1^2$	0.0694 0.0692	0.0200 0.0260	0.0146 0.0176	0.0207 0.0214
$F_2\sigma_2$	-0.1462 -0.1462	-0.2511 -0.2066	-0.3698 -0.3136	-0.4403 -0.4484
$F_{22}\sigma_2^2$	0.0067 0.0067	0.0197 0.0133	0.0427 0.0307	0.0606 0.0628
$F_3\sigma_3$	-0.0044 -0.0031	0.0146 0.0366	0.0054 0.0624	0.0509 0.0158
$F_{33}\sigma_3^2$	0.0000 0.0000	0.0001 0.0004	0.0000 0.0012	0.0008 0.0001
$F_{44}\tau_{23}^2$	0.0154 0.0151	0.0899 0.0670	0.1615 0.1161	0.0452 0.0426
$F_{55}\tau_{13}^2$	0.3320 0.3329	0.4864 0.4680	0.3947 0.3762	0.2114 0.2171
$F_{66}\tau_{12}^2$	0.5956 0.5939	0.5498 0.5149	0.6906 0.6431	0.9789 1.0154

A disappointing aspect of the predictions is the fact that the predicted far-field failure strains are very conservative compared to the strains determined experimentally [1]. This may be due to a number of factors including: low input values for the shear strength, nonlinear material behavior near the hole edge, the idealization of distinct interfaces which gives rise to a mathematical singularity and theoretical stresses which may be much higher than those present in a real laminate [5]. Future work will address many of these considerations.

CONCLUSIONS

Three dimensional finite element stress analysis of notched angle-ply laminates under compression loading and a failure analysis based upon the tensor polynomial failure criterion have been presented. The following conclusions for compression loading can be drawn from the results of the study:

- o 1/4 symmetry can be used to model failure
- o Failure initiates at the $\pm\phi$ interface
- o Failure is primarily due to τ_{12} and τ_{23} shear stresses
- o The angular location of initial failure varies with fiber orientation.
- o The predicted far-field failure strains are conservative

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